

**SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT OF RELIEF SERVICES ON THE WELL-BEING
OF EMERGENCY VICTIMS IN KANO STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This study assessed the social and psychological impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims in Kano State. The objectives are to determine the immediate needs of emergency victims; determine the social impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims; to determine the psychological impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims, and determine the relationship between social and psychological impact of relief services provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency (KSEMA). The study employed a survey research design with population of 52,661 subjects comprising of 287 staff and 52,374 emergency victims benefitted from the relief services provided by KSEMA in Kano State. The sample of the study was 390 based on the table for determining sample size by Krejcie and Morgan (2006). The sampling procedure used in this study was a purposive sampling procedure. In this study therefore, the researcher deliberately selected and involved 30 Officials of KSEMA and 360 emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services of KSEMA. However, in reaching out to the sampled beneficiaries a snowball technique was used. Two self-developed instruments were used in collection of data. These were a Questionnaire and a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Guide. While a 4-point Likert Scale type Questionnaire named "Questionnaire for Emergency Victims of KSEMA" (QEVKSEMA) for the emergency victims was used, an FGD was conducted with officials of KSEMA who were involved in the delivery of the relief services. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by experts. And the reliability of the instruments was obtained using the split-half method in which the reliability coefficient level of 0.074 was obtained. Data was analyzed through descriptive and inferential statistics and discussed qualitatively. Findings of the study revealed among others that the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State were security of lives and properties; comfortable shelter; essential food stuff; adequate medical facilities; reconstructions; sufficient monetary donations; adequate family welfare; counselling support; relationship building; livelihood activities, and spiritual needs to address social, and psychological challenges, and there is significant relationship between social and psychological impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims in Kano State, Nigeria. Recommendations made by the study include; Government of Kano State should provide adequate security of lives, properties, and insurance of goods and services of emergency victims so as to facilitate their social resettlement in to their families, religious, and cultural activities, and KSEMA should put hands together with other professional counsellors, Hisbah board and religious faith organizations in the provision of adequate counselling that will reduce the damages and the vulnerability among the emergency victims.

Keywords: Learned helplessness, Psychological adjustment, Relief services, Social welfare, Social work, and Trauma.

Introduction

Social welfare is a system of effective social service delivery through the utilization of government resources so as to promote the general well-being of the citizenry. The delivery of social welfare services has for long been carried out by various institutions. Apart from the services provided for the general well-being of the public which include; education, health, housing, transportation, security, and food security to mention few, there are other services provided to special categories of individuals expose to various personal, social, and psychological problems requiring special intervention within the context of emergency situations. Contemporarily, emergencies are the results of disasters such as fire outbreaks, insurgencies, flood, drought, desertification, and other forms of catastrophe that were eminent of traumatic experiences requiring social and psychological emergency responses. Such as means for livelihood (infrastructure, recreational facilities, cultural and traditional festivities, socio-psychological support, and counseling services.

Fire outbreak in Kano State has indeed assumed an alarming proportion as there is barely a day without occurrence of one incidence or the other leaving in its wake destruction of properties worth millions of naira, sometimes loss of lives, devastating impacts on human lives/livelihoods and infrastructural development. Apart from this, within the decade 2010-2019 most of the displaced persons who suffered several attacks of Boko-Haram terrorist have comprised of women, children, the old, and youth migrated in Kano State. In addition to these Kano State has been among the State in Nigeria that witnessed the 2012 flood disaster that drew responses from the public, federal, state and local governments, civil society organizations, and international development partners. These has caused the level in the increase of emergency victims whom were social, morally, and psychologically disturbed and found vulnerable to homelessness, crime, poverty, hunger, and many other social vices. In the urban cities of Kano some of the emergency victims of insurgencies were found wandering the streets engaged in begging. Others who lost their homes and farms were left unemployed, and some of them were in need of effective counseling service so as to cope with their traumatic experiences. However, in the rural areas most husbands whom were victims of drought runaway from their wives and children living them with no one to take care of them. Emergency victims are therefore in need of assistance that will facilitate them to re-settle back to their homes, religious/cultural engagement, and mental fitness. The social welfare need of these victims needs to be addressed properly by the relief agencies.

The theoretical framework for this study is based on the Learned Helplessness Theory developed by Seligman (1967). The theory posits that animals and people can learn that responding to situation controls rewards and punishment. Human beings and animals are all sensitive to the independence of responding and reinforcers and can learn that events are either uncontrollable or controllable. The theory stressed three main effects of uncontrollable trauma which provided for learning in terms of response initiation, retardation of learning and emotional stress.

- i) Response initiation; that is the probability that the subject will initiate responses to escape is lowered because part of the incentive for making such responses is the expectation that they will bring relief;
- ii) Retardation of learning; that is learning that responding and shock are independent and which makes it more difficult to learn that responding does produce relief, and
- iii) Emotional stress; that is learning that trauma is uncontrollable may produce more stress than learning that it is controllable. (Seligman and Maier, 1976).

This means that people affected by emergencies can either make some responses or refrain from making it, and thereby influence the events around them. This implies that nature, however, is not always so permissive in its arrangement of the contingencies. Furthermore, they suggested that such uncontrollable events can be significantly debilitating them producing passivity in the face of trauma, inability to learn that responding is effective and emotional stress and possibly depression. The theory is relevant to the study as it highlights the situation of helplessness that emergency victims face. It also demonstrated the varying patterns of responses to the helplessness conditions including the response in terms of relief support/services. These therefore creates the need for interventional measures, through active relief services provision and which are expected to make them helpful and hopeful, as well as gain resettlement into their various social and experience psychological stability. Furthermore, the experiences learned will allow for the emergency victims to have knowledge and skills as regards to disaster preparedness, management, and control.

Historically, social work is an old helping profession that originated in the 19th century as a result of the emergence of the Industrial Revolution (IR) when there was a great leap in technological and scientific arrangement. This led to frequent migration to urban areas throughout the Western Europe. This led to many social problems, which in turn led to an increase in social activism. However, efforts were made by the then missionaries as an attempt to resolve the problems inherent in the large cities like poverty, prostitution, disease, and other affliction. While in the United States, workers known as “friendly visitors” were paid by the church and other charitable bodies to work through direct relief, prayer, and evangelism to alleviate the problems. In Europe, chaplains or almoners were appointed to administer the church’s mission to the poor. During this time, rescue societies were initiated to find more appropriate means of self-support for women involved in prostitution. Mental asylums grew to assist in taking care of the mentally ill. However, a new philosophy of “scientific charity” emerged, which stated charity should be “secular, rational and empirical as opposed to sectarian, sentimental, and dogmatic” (Huff, 2008). Traditionally, the Extended Family Kinship System (EFS) had contributed immensely to the development of its members and the neighbourhood in the history of Nigeria. However, with a high level of increase in individualism and westernization of family values, as a result of nuclearization of life, the EFS could no longer effectively protect the family and the general public in the problematic areas of their existence in the State. Family responsibility has been among the objectives of social welfare since the Elizabethan Poor Laws in 1601, yet the total involvement of government in the welfare system has inadvertently eroded this role of the EFS in our society. According to Omolewa and Kazeem (1991) “the indigenous society was also a caring one, eager to ensure that no one in the society was deprived of the basic necessities of life”. However, in Nigeria, the formal social work practice opposed the traditional system after the 2nd World War. The pioneer of social work in Nigeria is the Salvation Army and the Green Triangle Group in Lagos. These groups were engaged in assisting the delinquents who have strayed away from the traditional and societal norms of the period. While the Salvation Army established industrial schools where delinquent children are sent for training and readjustment, the Green Triangle established boys and girls club where talents and other useful aspects of the life of the individual delinquents were established and improved (Omolewa and Kazeem 1991).

In the Nigerian context, therefore, the emergency victim’s nature and characteristics were those inculcated from disasters like, fire out-breaks, insurgencies, flood, and major accidents. The contemporary needs of the emergency victims include rehabilitation through active relief service provision in form of programmes such as emergency shelter (Camp), counselling, food items, non-food items, empowerment, vocational skill, infrastructure for restructuring, repatriation, education, monetary assistance, etc. Similarly, the demographics of emergency victims whom are the beneficiaries of relief services from the emergency management agency in Nigeria include gender, age, occupations, educational background, etc. Most of these emergency victims in Nigeria are vulnerable to various social problems such as homelessness, poverty, displacement, hunger, begging, prostitution, and many other social vices that deteriorated the living standards of people.

Statement of the Problem

In the modern-day, relief services are the immediate intervention organized and provided for the purpose of helping emergency victims whom were having various social problems requiring social and psychological adjustment in their societies. In Kano State therefore, there is the Kano State Emergency Management Agency (KSEMA) which was established in March 1999 by the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) Act No. 12 of 1999 and as amended by the Act No.50 of 1999 to manage disasters in all its ramifications. This paper therefore is intended to draw the implication of the Learned Helplessness Theory developed by Seligman and Maier (1976) on the situation of helplessness that emergency victims face, determine social and psychological relief services provided to emergency victims, and determine the relationship between social and psychological impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims in Kano State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to draw the implication of the Learned Helplessness Theory developed by Seligman and Maier (1976) on the situation of helplessness that emergency victims face.

Other objectives of the study are:

- i. To determine the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State;
- ii. To determine the social impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency;
- iii. To determine the psychological impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency, and
- iv. To determine the relationship between social and psychological impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims in Kano State, Nigeria.

Study Questions

The following questions guided the conduct of the study:

- i. What are the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State?
- ii. What is the social impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency?
- iii. What is the psychological impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency?

Study Hypothesis:

The following null hypothesis was tested during the study:

Ho1, there is no significant relationship between social and psychological impact of relief services provided by KSEMA

Methodology

This study employed a survey research design with population of 52,661 subjects comprising of 287 staffs and 52,374 emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services provided by SEMA in Kano State. The sample of the study was 390 based on the table for determining sample size by Krejcie and Morgan (2006). The sampling procedure used in this study was a purposive sampling procedure. In this study therefore, the researcher selected and involved 30 Officials of KSEMA and 360 emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services of KSEMA purposefully. However, in reaching out to the sampled beneficiaries a snowball technique was used. Two self-developed instruments were used in the collection of data. These were a Questionnaire and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Guide. A 4-point Likert Scale type Questionnaire named "Questionnaire for Emergency Victims of KSEMA" (QEVKSEMA) for the emergency victims was used, an FGD was conducted with Officials of KSEMA who were involved in the delivery of the relief services. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by experts in measurement and evaluation, social work, and emergency management. And the reliability of the instruments was obtained using the split-half method in which the reliability coefficient level of 0.074 was obtained. Data was analyzed through descriptive statistics using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21. While the data collected through the FGD with the staff involved in the delivery of relief services provided to emergency victims by KSEMA was reported verbatim and discussed qualitatively, the data retrieved and processed on the SPSS was presented in descriptive statistics in form of frequency (F) and percentage (%), mean (X) as well as cumulative mean score that indicated a decision from the analysis. However, the decision rule for the acceptance of the statement on items of the questionnaire was obtained by calculating $SA=4, + A=3 + D=2 + SD=1$ which was equal to 10 divided by 4 = 2.5. This means that a cumulative-mean score at or above 2.50 indicated the acceptance of the statement on the items of the questionnaire. As such any cumulative mean score below 2.50 justified statements on the items of the questionnaire were rejected. In addition to this, the null hypothesis was tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics and decision at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

Results

Study question 1. What are the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State?

This research question was answered and the result is presented in table 1.

Table 1. The immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State

Immediate needs	SA		A		D		SD		X	Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Security of life and property	188	54.2	81	23.3	36	10.4	42	12.1	3.1960	Agreed
Comfortable shelter	158	45.5	116	33.4	32	9.2	41	11.8	3.1268	Agreed
Essential food stuff	172	49.6	106	30.5	39	11.2	30	8.6	3.2104	Agreed
Adequate medical facilities	129	37.2	127	36.6	57	16.4	34	9.8	3.0115	Agreed
Reconstruction	87	25.1	145	41.8	65	18.7	50	14.4	2.7752	Agreed
Sufficient monetary donation and adequate family welfare to emergency victims	105	30.3	158	45.5	34	9.8	50	14.4	2.9164	Agreed
Counselling support needs to address traumatic experience	73	21.0	176	50.7	65	18.7	33	9.5	2.8329	Agreed
Relationship building support needs to address social isolation	81	23.3	177	51.0	53	15.3	36	10.4	2.8732	Agreed
Livelihood activities support needs to address economic challenges	98	28.2	167	48.1	40	11.5	42	12.1	2.9251	Agreed
Spiritual needs to address social life changes	89	25.6	120	34.6	80	23.1	58	16.7	2.6916	Agreed
Cumulative mean= 2.95										

Table 1 above described the statements on the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State. According to the table, responses on the statement on security of life and property of the respondents were strongly agreed by 54.2% of the sampled respondents. This was followed by 23.3% of the respondents who agreed with the said statement on security of life and property. While 12.1% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement, only 10.4% of the respondents disagreed with the statement on security of life and property as immediate need of the respondents. When the statement on comfortable shelter as an immediate need of the emergency victims was stated, 45.5% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement. This was followed by 33.4% of the respondents who opined that comfortable shelter was an immediate need of emergency victims. While a small percentage of 9.2 disagreed with the said statement, only 11.8% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement that comfortable shelter was an immediate need of emergency victims. However, respondents whom strongly agreed that essential food stuff was an immediate need of emergency victims constituted 49.6%. This was followed by a reasonable percentage of 30.5 whom agreed with the said statement. Added to this were 11.2% of the respondents whom disagreed with the said statement. This was complemented with the remaining 8.6% of the respondents

whom strongly disagreed with the statement on essential food stuff was an immediate need of emergency victims. Regarding the statement that adequate medical facilities was an immediate need of emergency victims, respondents whom strongly agreed and those agreed with the statement were closely having the sound percentages of 37.2 and 36.6. These were followed by the respondents whom disagreed with the said statement constituted 16.4%. The remaining 9.8% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement that adequate medical facilities were an immediate need of emergency victims. Furthermore, 41.8% of the sampled respondents agreed with the statement that reconstruction was an immediate need of emergency victims. This was however followed by 25.1% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with said statement. While 18.7% of the respondents disagreed with the said statement, a reasonable percentage of 14.4 strongly disagreed with the statement that reconstruction was an immediate need of emergency victims. Looking in to the table, it is observed that highest percentage 45.5 of the respondents agreed with the statement that sufficient monetary donation and adequate family welfare was an immediate need of the emergency victims. This was followed by 30.3% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement. While 14.4% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement, only 9.8% of the respondents disagreed with the statement that sufficient monetary donation and adequate family welfare was an immediate need of the emergency victims. It has been observed that 50.7% of the respondents agreed with the statement that counselling support needs to address traumatic experience were an immediate need of emergency victims. This was complemented by 21% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement. While a sound percentage of 18.7 disagreed with the statement, only 9.5% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement that counselling support needs to address traumatic experience was an immediate need of emergency victims. In addition to this were 51% of the respondents whom agreed with the statement that relationship building support needs to address social isolation were the immediate needs of emergency victims. This was followed by 23.3% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement. While a negligible percentage of 10.4 strongly disagreed with the said statement, a sound percentage of 15.3 disagreed with the statement that relationship building support needs to address social isolation were the immediate needs of emergency victims. Moreover, 48.1% of the respondents agreed with the statement that livelihood activities support needs to address economic challenges were the immediate needs of emergency victims. Only 28.2% of the respondents strongly agreed with the said statement. Those respondents whom disagreed and those strongly disagreed with the statement that livelihood activities support needs to address economic challenges were the immediate needs of emergency victims were closely having the percentages of 11.5 and 12.1. While 25.6% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that spiritual needs to address social life challenges were the immediate needs of emergency victims, highest percentage of 34.6 agreed with the statement. Unlike 23.1% of the respondents whom disagreed with the statement and the other 16.7% whom also strongly disagreed with the statement that spiritual need to address social life challenges were the immediate needs of emergency victims. These statements on the immediate needs of emergency victims were considered accepted by the respondents as justified by the cumulative mean score of 2.95 higher than the decision rule of 2.50 in favour of the acceptance of the statements provided in the items of the questionnaire.

Study Question 2: What is the social impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency?

This research question was answered by the sampled emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services provided by KSEMA in simple frequency counts, percentages, mean score, and cumulative mean, where n=347.

Table 2: The social impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency

Social impact	SA		A		D		SD		X	Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to religious activities	68	19.6	139	40.1	92	26.5	48	13.8	2.6542	Agreed
Relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for sustenance of important/crucial social engagements such as marriage ceremonies, and festivals, etc	50	14.4	195	56.2	76	21.9	26	7.5	2.7752	Agreed
Relief services provided by KSEMA ensured full participation in community development activities	65	18.7	197	56.8	55	15.9	30	8.6	2.8559	Agreed
Relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for Maintenance of family stability	82	23.6	138	39.8	105	30.3	22	6.3	2.8069	Agreed
Relief services provided by KSEMA encouraged significant cultural activities such as appropriate mode of dressing, visitations, and sharing of goods and services	53	15.3	190	54.8	64	18.4	40	11.5	2.7378	Agreed
Relief services provided by KSEMA facilitated leisure and recreation activities	50	14.4	133	38.3	118	34.0	46	13.3	2.5389	Agreed
Relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to emergency education programmes	48	13.8	146	42.1	55	15.9	98	28.2	2.4150	Disagreed
Relief services provided by KSEMA enhanced access to health services	50	14.4	143	41.2	115	33.1	39	11.2	2.5879	Agreed
Cumulative mean= 2.67									7	

From the above table 2, 40.1% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to religious activities. And a sound percentage of 19.6 strongly agreed with the said statement. In addition to this, the highest percentage of 56.2 was constituted by the respondents whom agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for sustenance of important/crucial social engagements such as marriage ceremonies, and festivals, etc. this was followed by 14.4% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the statement. Furthermore, 56.8% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA ensured full participation in community development activities. These were followed by 18.7% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement. However, 39.8% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for maintenance of family stability. This was followed by 23.6% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement. Similarly, 54.8% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA encourage significant cultural activities such as appropriate mode of dressing, visitations, and sharing of goods and services. These were followed by a sound percentage of 15.3 strongly agreed with the statement. Accordingly, 38.3% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA facilitated leisure and recreational activities, a small percentage of 14.4% strongly agreed with the said statement. Added to these were those 42.1% of the respondents whom agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to emergency education programmes. This was followed by 13.8% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to emergency education programmes. However, 41.2% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA enhance access to health services. This was followed by a reasonable percentage of 14.4 whom agreed with the statement. These statements were considered accepted by the respondents as justified by the cumulative mean score of 2.67 higher than the decision rule of 2.50 in favour of acceptance of the items in the questionnaire.

Study Question 3: What is the psychological impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency?

This research question was answered and presented in table 6.

Table 3. The psychological impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency

Psychological impact	SA		A		D		SD		X	Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Relief services provided by KSEMA ensured adequate counselling services for emergency victims	78	22.5	141	40.6	96	27.7	32	9.2	2.7637	Agreed
Relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for regular spiritual preaching for emergency victims	57	16.4	204	58.8	58	16.7	28	8.1	2.8357	Agreed
Relief services provided by KSEMA facilitated early recovery to socio-economic life and reduced damages to emergency victim's psychological stability	66	19.0	149	42.9	57	16.4	75	21.6	2.5937	Agreed
Relief services provided by KSEMA served to prevent stigmatization of emergency victims	83	23.9	118	34.0	71	20.5	75	21.6	2.6023	Agreed
Relief services provided by KSEMA encouraged prompt and adequate psychological support at the earliest possible time for emergency victims	61	17.6	150	43.2	60	17.3	76	21.9	2.5648	Agreed
Relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to vital information on health, trauma and access to services for emergency victims	60	17.3	136	39.2	109	31.4	42	12.1	2.6167	Agreed
Relief services provided by KSEMA prevented depression among the emergency victims	67	19.3	155	44.7	94	27.1	31	8.9	2.7435	Agreed
Relief services provided by KSEMA prevented loneliness and reduced vulnerability among the emergency victims	63	18.2	136	39.2	114	32.9	34	9.8	2.6571	Agreed
Cumulative mean = 2.67									9	

According to the table 3 above on the psychological impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by KSEMA, 40.6% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA ensured adequate counselling services for emergency victims. This was opposite by the respondents whom disagreed with the said statement constituted 27.7%. While 22.5% of the respondents strongly agreed with the said statement, only 9.2% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA ensured adequate counselling services for emergency victims. Added to this was the highest percentage of 58.8 whom agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for regular spiritual preaching for emergency victims. This was followed by 16.7% of the respondents whom disagreed with the said statement. While a reasonable percentage of 16.4 strongly agreed with the said statement, a small percentage of 8.1 strongly disagreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for regular spiritual preaching for emergency victims. Similarly, 42.9% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA facilitated early recovery to socio-economic life reduced damage to emergency victim's psychological stability. This was followed by 21.6% of the respondents whom strongly disagreed with the said statement. While 19% of the respondents strongly agreed with the said statement, only 16.4% of the respondents disagreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA facilitated early recovery to socio-economic life reduced damage to emergency victim's psychological stability. However, 34% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA served to prevent stigmatization of emergency victims. This was followed by 23.9% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement. While 21.6% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the said statement, only 20.5% of the respondents disagreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA served to prevent stigmatization of emergency victims. Accordingly, 43.2% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA encouraged prompt and adequate psychological support at the earliest possible time for emergency victims. This was followed by 21.9% of the respondents whom strongly disagreed with the said statement. While 17.6% of the respondents strongly agreed with the said statement, only 17.3% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA encouraged prompt and adequate psychological support at the earliest possible time for emergency victims. Moreover, the respondents whom strongly agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to vital information on health, trauma, and access to services for emergency victims constituted the highest percentage of 39.2. This was followed by 31.4% of the respondents whom disagreed with the said statement. While 17.3% of the respondents strongly agreed with the said statement, a small percentage of 12.1 strongly disagreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to vital information on health, trauma, and access to services for emergency victims. However, the highest percentages of 44.7 were those respondents whom agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA prevented depression among the emergency victims. These were followed by 27.1% of the respondents whom disagreed with the said statement. While 19.3% of the respondents strongly agreed with the said statement, only 8.9% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA prevented depression among the emergency victims. Added to this were the respondents whom agreed with statement that relief services provided by KSEMA prevented loneliness and reduced vulnerability among the emergency victims constituted 39.2%. This were opposite by 32.9% of the respondents whom disagreed with the said statement. While a sound percentage of 18.2 strongly agreed with the said statement, a small percentage of 9.8 strongly disagreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA prevented loneliness and reduced vulnerability among the emergency victims. These statements were considered accepted by the respondents as justified by the cumulative mean score of 2.67 higher than the decision rule of 2.50.

Hypothesis Testing

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between social and psychological impact of relief services provided by KSEMA

Below is the table for Ho1:

Table 4: Social and psychological impact relationship

Variable	N	X	r	P	Remark
Social Impact	347	2.67	.548	0.40	SR
Psychological Impact	347	2.67			

Table 4 above indicated a positive relationship between social impact and psychological impact of relief services provided by KSEMA. Since the probability value is less than 0.05 level of significant. The calculated P- value is 0.040 which is less than the initial P-value of 0.05. This shows that the null hypothesis (Ho1) is rejected. And it indicated that there is significant relationship between the social impact and psychological impact of relief services provided by KSEMA.

Findings

From the proceeding data analysis, the following findings were deduced:

- i) The immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State were security of lives and properties; comfortable shelter; essential food stuff; adequate medical facilities; reconstructions; sufficient monetary donations; adequate family welfare; counselling support; relationship building; livelihood activities, and spiritual needs to address social, and psychological challenges;
- ii) The social impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by KSEMA are having access to religious activities; sustenance of social engagement; full participation in community development activities; maintenance of family stability; significant cultural activities; leisure and recreational activities; ensured access to emergency education programmes, and enhanced access to health services by the emergency victims;
- iii) The psychological impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by KSEMA were having ensured adequate counselling services; allowed for regular spiritual preaching; facilitated early recovery to socio-economic life; served to prevent stigmatization; encouraged prompt and adequate psychological support; ensured access to vital information on health and trauma; prevented depression, and prevented loneliness and reduced vulnerability among the emergency victims, and
- iv) There is significant relationship between social and psychological impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims in Kano State, Nigeria, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of findings

The first finding of this study on the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State was related to the findings of the studies conducted by Aminu (2018). This study identified security, housing, accommodation, feeding, medication, clothing, education, empowerment, job, and repatriation as the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kumbotso local government area of Kano State. In addition to this and in a study conducted by Aujara, (2018) entitled an examination of community education needs of Internally Displaced Persons in Borno State, Nigeria. The study justified the level of educational attainment; community education needs; and scope of community education programmes for the IDPs living in IDPs Camps in Borno State. These included vocational education, civic and citizenship education, entrepreneurial and environmental education. Furthermore, in a study undertaken by Silove, Steel, & Psychol (2006) entitled understanding community psychosocial needs after disaster: implications for mental health services. The studied maintained that the psycho-social needs of victims of disasters need to be address. Priorities should be pursued in relation to mental health interventions, with most controversy surrounding the relevance of traumatic stress to mental health among the emergency victims. The views by the researcher suggested that acute traumatic stress may be a normative response to life threat which tends to subside once conditions of

safety are established. At the same time, there was a residual minority of emergency victims whom might continue to experience chronic posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and their needs can be easily overlooked. Therefore it is of great importance to address the needs of emergency victims based on their opinions regarding what may have implications to their well-being during resettlement in to their various families, communities, and occupations.

The second finding of the study which revealed that the social impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by KSEMA were having access to religious activities; sustenance of social engagement; full participation in community development activities; maintenance of family stability; encouraged significant cultural activities; facilitated leisure and recreational activities; ensured access to emergency education programmes, and enhanced access to health services by the emergency victims. This finding is in line with the opinions of the staff of KSEMA involved in the provision of relief services to the emergency victims during the FGD. Accordingly, their response thus; the social impact of relief services on the well-being of the emergency victims as provided by KSEMA are *“been able to fully engaged in social activities such as attending religious congregations, festivals, and ceremonies; maintenance of family stability, recreation, dressing and make-up, and participation in community developmental activities by the emergency victims”*. Contrary to these responses were those findings justified in the seventh consecutive report by the Salvation Army in the national Economic and Social Impact Survey (ESIS) 2018. The study is an adjunct to the ESIS 2018 report and is a summary of the main themes and key findings. This provided a deeper understanding of the experiences of hardship, with a particular focus on the cost of living and housing situations for those participants who accessed Doorways Emergency Relief (ER) services in Australia. The findings of the study revealed that a large proportion of respondents who accessed the Salvation Army’s Emergency Relief services experienced financial hardship and disadvantage; homelessness and unemployment; inability to seek support from friends and family in a time of crisis; food insecurity; poor response to parenting responsibilities, and lack of and cost of transportation. The well-being of the beneficiaries of the emergency relief has been impacted negatively.

The third finding of this study which revealed that the psychological impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by KSEMA were having ensured adequate counselling services; allowed for regular spiritual preaching; facilitated early recovery to socio-economic life; served to preventing of stigmatization; encouraged prompt and adequate psychological support; ensured access to vital information on health and trauma; prevented depression, and prevented loneliness and reduced vulnerability among the emergency victims. These were confirmed during the FGD as well thus: the psychological impacts of relief services on the well-being of the emergency victims as provided by KSEMA were adjustment from problematic to non-problematic conditions, reduction of stigmatization, maintenance of mental stability, and reduction of vulnerability among the emergency victims. This finding was however relates with the justifications of various scholars within the scope of this study. Accordingly, at some stage in an emergency, people may experience complex emotional, spiritual, social and physical impacts. Some of these are injuries to biological, mental and social aspects of the person’s personality and they require early stabilization and support, just as physical injuries do. In the immediate repercussion of an emergency, people are vulnerable and there is potential for insensitive and uninformed management to seriously aggravate existing psychosocial injuries or cause additional harm. Psychological support is designed to prevent this. Early interventional support through relief services remained active for the well-being of emergency victims. The importance of early intervention cannot be overstated. Planning for and providing supports during an emergency and in early recovery can reduce the likelihood of more serious and long-term damage to people’s psychological and social well-being. Everyone involved in responding to an emergency can have a positive impact on people’s emotional and physical recovery. Emergency responders can do this by ensuring people feel safe, helping people to help themselves, keeping families and groups together, being calm and hopeful, preserving privacy and dignity, and facilitating early access to physical and emotional support.

The last finding of the study revealed that there is significant relationship between social and psychological impact of relief services provided by KSEMA. The null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that a significant relationship exists between the social and psychological impact of relief services provided by KSEMA. The finding is in line with the findings reported in the study conducted by Enwemeka (2014) entitled the Administration of Emergency Relief Programme in Nigeria: A Case of Flood Incident in Delta

State, the objectives of the study were to examine the relationship between the pattern of administration of emergence relief programme and effective emergency management and administration of relief programmes in Delta State; to ascertain whether administration of emergency relief programmes has really ameliorates the suffering of the flood victims in Delta State; to assess the effects of inadequate government policies on disaster management and poor funding on disaster management agencies in Delta State; and to suggest measures towards reducing occurrence and management of disasters as well as improving the administration of emergency relief programmes in Nigeria. Data used in the study was collected from both primary and secondary sources in which the primary sources. Findings revealed included the administration of emergency relief programmes in Nigeria particularly in Delta State has suffered a setback following the ineffectiveness of the public/government agencies discharged with disaster management and the pattern of administration of emergency relief programmes in Delta State create management problems especially in ensuring equitable distribution of relief materials. The study recommended among others that government should provide adequate relief materials to flood victims in the flood prone areas in Nigeria and contingency planning which will provide preventive solutions such as construction of drainages and evacuation of flood danger zones to safer places.

Conclusion

It was observed that relief services rendered to emergency victims can impact not only on their well-being, but also on improving on their socio-psychological being, hence, humanitarian support services can also arise from counselling perspectives. Also humanitarian development during crises or disasters comprised of individual and family counselling, vocational support services in form of psycho-counseling service and occupational training that address the traumatic experiences and enhance better adjustment within the societies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i) Government of Kano State should provide adequate security of lives, properties, and insurance of goods and services of emergency victims so as to facilitate their social resettlement in to their families, religious, and cultural activities, and
- ii) KSEMA should put hands together with other professional counsellors, Hisbah board and religious faith organizations in the provision of adequate counselling that will reduce the damages and the vulnerability among the emergency victims.

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